

BUCKLING ANALYSES OF FIBER COMPOSITE LAMINATE PLATES WITH MATERIAL NONLINEARITY

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ABSTRACT

A nonlinear material constitutive model, including a nonlinear in-plane shear formulation and a failure criterion, for fiber-composite laminate materials is employed to carry out finite-element buckling analyses for composite plates under uniaxial compressive loads. It has been shown that the nonlinear in-plane shear together with the failure criterion have significant influence on the buckling behavior of composite laminate plates.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the literature, most stability studies of composite laminate plates have been limited to geometrically nonlinear analyses [1,2]. Little attention has been paid to the material nonlinearity. It is known that unidirectional fibrous composites exhibit severe nonlinearity in in-plane shear stress-strain relation. In addition, deviation from linearity is also observed in transverse loadings but the degree of nonlinearity is not comparable to that in the in-plane shear [3]. For graphite/epoxy and boron/epoxy, this nonlinearity associated with the transverse loadings can usually be ignored [4].

A significant number of macromechanical models have been proposed to represent the constitutive relation of fiber-composite materials [3,5-7]. In addition, various failure criteria have also been proposed to predict the onset of failure in single layer of fiber-reinforced composites, such as maximum stress theory, Tsai-Wu theory, Hoffman theory, etc. [8]. Since the nonlinearity of in-plane shear is significant for composite materials, this work is focusing on the influence of the in-plane shear nonlinearity together with a failure criterion on the buckling response of composite plates. In this paper, a material model including the nonlinear in-plane shear and the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is reviewed first. Then, nonlinear buckling analyses for simply supported composite plates under uniaxial compression are carried out using the ABAQUS finite element program [9] and are compared with those using linear material properties.

2. CONSTITUTIVE MODELLING OF LAMINA

For fiber-composite laminate materials, each lamina can be considered as an

orthotropic layer in a plane stress condition. The incremental constitutive matrices for a linear orthotropic lamina in the material coordinates can be written as

$$\Delta\{\sigma'\} = [Q_1'] \Delta\{\epsilon'\} \quad \Delta\{\tau_t'\} = [Q_2'] \Delta\{\gamma_t'\} \quad (1)$$

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix}, \quad [Q_2'] = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_2 G_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\{\sigma'\} = \Delta\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}\}^T$, $\Delta\{\tau_t'\} = \Delta\{\tau_{13}, \tau_{23}\}^T$, $\Delta\{\epsilon'\} = \Delta\{\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \gamma_{12}\}^T$, and $\Delta\{\gamma_t'\} = \Delta\{\gamma_{13}, \gamma_{23}\}^T$. The α_1 and α_2 are the shear correction factors and are taken to be 0.83. To model the nonlinear in-plane shear behavior, the nonlinear strain-stress relation for a composite lamina suggested by Hahn and Tsai [3] is adopted in this study, which is given as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{11}} & \frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} + S_{6666} \tau_{12}^2 \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In this model only one constant S_{6666} is required to account for the in-plane shear nonlinearity. The value of S_{6666} can be determined by a curve fit to various off-axis tension test data [3]. Inverting and differentiating Eq. (3), we can obtain the nonlinear incremental constitutive matrix for the lamina as follows:

$$[Q_1'] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1/G_{12} + 3S_{6666}\tau_{12}^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3. FAILURE CRITERION AND DEGRADATION OF STIFFNESS

Among existing failure criteria, the Tsai-Wu criterion [10] has been extensively used in literature and it is adopted in this analysis. Under plane stress conditions, this failure criterion has the following form

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\sigma_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (5a)$$

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{X} + \frac{1}{X'}, \quad F_2 = \frac{1}{Y} + \frac{1}{Y'}, \quad F_{11} = \frac{-1}{XX'}, \quad F_{22} = \frac{-1}{YY'}, \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{S^2} \quad (5b)$$

The X , Y and X' , Y' are the lamina longitudinal and transverse strengths in tension and compression, respectively, and S is the shear strength of the lamina. Though

the stress interaction term F_{12} in Eq. (5a) is difficult to be determined, it has been suggested by Narayanaswami and Adelman [11] that F_{12} can be set equal to zero for practical applications. Hence, $F_{12} = 0$ is used in this investigation. It is known that the Tsai-Wu criterion does not distinguish failure modes. Thus, when failure of a ply occurs according to Eq. (5a), the following two rules are used to determine whether the ply failure is caused by resin fracture or fiber breakage [8]:

- (1) If a ply fails but the stress in the fiber direction remains less than the uniaxial strength of the lamina in the fiber direction, i.e. $X' < \sigma_1 < X$, the ply failure is assumed to be resin induced. The laminate loses its capability to support transverse and shear stresses, but remains to carry longitudinal stress. The constitutive matrix of the lamina becomes

$$[Q'_1] = \begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

- (2) If a ply fails with σ_1 exceeding the uniaxial strength of the lamina, the ply failure is caused by the fiber breakage and a total ply rupture is assumed. The constitutive matrix of the lamina becomes

$$[Q'_1] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

4. CONSTITUTIVE MODELLING OF COMPOSITE SHELL SECTION

The elements used in the finite-element analysis are eight-node isoparametric shell elements with six degrees of freedom per node. The formulation of the shell allows transverse shear deformation and these shear flexible shells can be used for both thick and thin shell analysis [9]. In the analysis, the constitutive matrix of composite materials at the integration points of shell elements must be calculated before the stiffness matrices are assembled from the element level to the structural level. For composite materials, the incremental constitutive equations of a lamina in the element coordinates (x, y, z) can be written as:

$$\Delta\{\sigma\} = [Q_1] \Delta\{\epsilon\}, \quad [Q_1] = [T_1]^T [Q'_1] [T_1] \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta\{\tau_t\} = [Q_2] \Delta\{\gamma_t\}, \quad [Q_2] = [T_2]^T [Q'_2] [T_2] \quad (9)$$

$$[T_1] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\phi & \sin^2\phi & \sin\phi\cos\phi \\ \sin^2\phi & \cos^2\phi & -\sin\phi\cos\phi \\ -2\sin\phi\cos\phi & 2\sin\phi\cos\phi & \cos^2\phi - \sin^2\phi \end{bmatrix}, \quad [T_2] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\phi & \sin\phi \\ -\sin\phi & \cos\phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta\{\sigma\} = \Delta\{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}^T$, $\Delta\{\tau_t\} = \Delta\{\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}^T$, $\Delta\{\epsilon\} = \Delta\{\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}\}^T$, and $\Delta\{\gamma_t\} = \Delta\{\gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}\}^T$. The ϕ is measured counterclockwise from the element local x -axis to the material 1-axis. Assume $\Delta\{\epsilon_0\} = \Delta\{\epsilon_{x0}, \epsilon_{y0}, \gamma_{xy0}\}^T$ are incremental in-plane strains at the mid-surface of the shell section and $\Delta\{\kappa\} = \Delta\{\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}\}^T$ are incremental curvatures. The incremental in-plane strains at a distance z from the

mid-surface of the shell section become

$$\Delta\{\varepsilon\} = \Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} + z\Delta\{\kappa\} \quad (11)$$

Let h be the total thickness of the shell section, the incremental stress resultants, $\Delta\{N\} = \Delta\{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T$, $\Delta\{M\} = \Delta\{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T$ and $\Delta\{V\} = \Delta\{V_x, V_y\}$, can be defined as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{N\} \\ \Delta\{M\} \\ \Delta\{V\} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{\sigma\} \\ z\Delta\{\sigma\} \\ \Delta\{\tau_t\} \end{Bmatrix} dz = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \begin{bmatrix} [Q_1] & z[Q_1] & [0] \\ z[Q_1] & z^2[Q_1] & [0] \\ [0]^T & [0]^T & [Q_2] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} \\ \Delta\{\kappa\} \\ \Delta\{\gamma_t\} \end{Bmatrix} dz \quad (12)$$

where $[0]$ is a 3 by 2 matrix with all the coefficients equal to zero. For the nonlinear material case, the $[Q_1]$ matrix in Eq. (8) can be taken from Eqs. (4), (6) or (7) and the incremental stress resultants of Eq. (12) can be obtained by a numerical integration through the thickness of the composite shell section. For the linear material case, the $[Q_1]$ matrix used in Eq. (8) is taken from Eq. (3) and the incremental stress resultants of the shell section can be written as a summation of integrals over the n laminae in the following form:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{N\} \\ \Delta\{M\} \\ \Delta\{V\} \end{Bmatrix} = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \begin{bmatrix} (z_{jt}-z_{jb})[Q_1] & \frac{1}{2}(z_{jt}^2-z_{jb}^2)[Q_1] & [0] \\ \frac{1}{2}(z_{jt}^2-z_{jb}^2)[Q_1] & \frac{1}{3}(z_{jt}^3-z_{jb}^3)[Q_1] & [0] \\ [0]^T & [0]^T & (z_{jt}-z_{jb})[Q_2] \end{bmatrix} \right) \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\{\varepsilon_0\} \\ \Delta\{\kappa\} \\ \Delta\{\gamma_t\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where z_{jt} and z_{jb} are distances from the mid-surface of the section to the top and the bottom of the j -th layer respectively.

5. NONLINEAR FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

In the ABAQUS finite element program, the nonlinear response of a structure is modeled by an updated Lagrangian formulation and a modified Riks nonlinear incremental algorithm [12] can be used to construct the equilibrium solution path. To model bifurcation from the prebuckling path to the postbuckling path, geometric imperfections of composite plates are introduced by superimposing a small fraction (say 0.001 of the plate thickness) of the lowest eigenmode determined by a linearized buckling analysis to the original nodal coordinates of plates.

6. NUMERICAL ANALYSES

6.1 Composite Plates with $[90/0]_{2S}$ and $[45/-45]_{2S}$ Layups

In this section, composite square plates with two laminate layups, $[90/0]_{2S}$ and $[45/-45]_{2S}$, are analyzed. Ply constitutive properties and plate geometry are given in Fig. 1. The linear and nonlinear in-plane shear stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 2. Both plates are subjected to uniform uniaxial compressive loads in the x direction. The edges of the plates are simply supported, which prevents out of plane motions but allows in-plane movements in x and y directions. In the numerical analysis, the entire plate is modeled by 36 shell elements.

The load-displacement curves for the $[90/0]_{2S}$ composite plate are plotted in Fig. 3. The N_x is the total force (positive value means compression) applied to the edges and u_x is the associated end displacement (positive value means end extension and negative value means end shortening). It can be seen that the curves computed by using linear and nonlinear in-plane shear formulations are very close. Hence, nonlinear in-plane shear alone does not have much influence on the buckling and postbuckling responses of this plate. For the analysis carried out using the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation together with the Tsai-Wu criterion, the composite plate behaves almost linearly until a sudden collapse of the plate occurs. The calculated failure load is about 99% of the linearized buckling load.

Figure 4 plots the load-displacement curves for the plate with a $[45/-45]_{2S}$ layup. With this kind of laminate layup, each lamina in the composite plate is subjected to severe shear loading. Therefore, it is a good sample to test the influence of nonlinear in-plane shear and failure theory on the buckling behavior of the plate. On contrary to the previous case, with the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation alone, the plate exhibit very nonlinear behavior throughout the entire loading stage. The load carrying capacity for the plate with the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation is much less than that with the linear shear formulation. For the analysis carried out using the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation together with the Tsai-Wu criterion, this plate exhibits a sudden failure mode while the loading is very low. The calculated failure strength of the composite plate is only about 19% of the linearized buckling load.

6.2 Composite Plates with $[\pm\theta/90/0]_S$ Layups

In this section, the $[\pm\theta/90/0]_S$ composite laminate plates are analyzed. The geometric and material properties, loading and finite element mesh of the plates are the same as those in the previous section. Figures 5 to 8 show the load-displacement curves for plates with θ equal to 0° , 30° , 60° and 90° . It can be observed that nonlinear in-plane shear alone does not have much influence on the buckling and postbuckling responses of these plates. For the analysis carried out using the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation together with the Tsai-Wu criterion, the composite plates with θ equal to 0° and 90° (Figs. 5 and 8) behave almost linearly until a sudden collapse of the plates occur. This is because that all the laminae of the composite plates fail at about the same time. On the other hand, the plates with θ equal to 30° and 60° (Figs. 6 and 7) exhibit progressive failure mechanisms. Though partial laminae of these plates have failed, the plates can still carry some limited load until the failure of all laminae have taken place.

In Fig. 9 the calculated ultimate strengths of $[\pm\theta/90/0]_S$ composite plates using the nonlinear shear formulation together with the Tsai-Wu criterion are compared with those obtained by the linearized buckling analyses. One can see that the calculated ultimate strengths of the plates with θ between 0° and 20° and with θ close to 90° are very close to the linearized buckling loads. On the other hand the calculated ultimate strengths of the plates with θ between 30° and 80° are much lower than the linearized buckling loads. One can also see that the optimal angle θ for the plates with the material nonlinear analysis is around 20° . This is quite different from that with linearized buckling analysis, which is between 40° and 50° .

7. CONCLUSIONS

For the material nonlinear buckling analysis of composite plates with various laminate layups, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The nonlinear in-plane shear alone does not have much influence on the buckling behavior of the plates with $[90/0]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta/90/0]_S$ layups.
2. The nonlinear in-plane shear together with material failure according to the Tsai-Wu theory has great influence on the buckling and postbuckling responses of the plates with $[90/0]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta/90/0]_S$ layups. Its effect on the reduction of ultimate strengths and postbuckling stiffness of these plates depends on the laminate layups.
3. The nonlinear in-plane shear alone has significant influence on the buckling response of the plate with a $[45/-45]_{2S}$ layup. In addition, if the Tsai-Wu criterion is considered, the calculated ultimate strength of the composite plate is much lower than the linearized buckling load.
4. The optimal fiber angle θ for $[\pm\theta/90/0]_S$ composite plates with the analysis using the nonlinear in-plane shear formulation and the Tsai-Wu failure theory is quite different from that obtained using the linearized buckling analysis.

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Laminate layups:	Plate geometry:
[90/0] _{2S}	L = 10.16 cm (4 in.)
[45/-45] _{2S}	t = 0.81cm (0.32 in.)
Ply constitutive properties:	Ply strengths:
E ₁₁ = 138 GPa	X = 1450 MPa
E ₂₂ = 14.5 GPa	X' = -1450 MPa
G ₁₂ = G ₁₃ = 5.86 GPa	Y = 52 MPa
G ₂₃ = 3.52 GPa	Y' = -206 MPa
ν ₁₂ = 0.21	S = 93 MPa
S ₆₆₆₆ = 7.31 (GPa) ⁻³	

Fig. 1 Geometric and material properties for Graphite/Epoxy composite laminate plate

Fig. 2 In-plane shear stress-strain curves for composite lamina

Fig. 3 Load-displacement curves for [90/0]_{2S} composite plate under uniaxial compression

Fig. 4 Load-displacement curves for $[45/-45]_2$ composite plate under uniaxial compression

Fig. 5 Load-displacement curves for $[+0/90/0]_s$ composite plate under uniaxial compression

Fig. 6 Load-displacement curves for $[+30/90/0]_s$ composite plate under uniaxial compression

Fig. 7 Load-displacement curves for $[+60/90/0]_s$ composite plate under uniaxial compression

Fig. 8 Load-displacement curves for $[+90/90/0]_s$ composite plate under uniaxial compression

Fig. 9 Critical load N_{xcr} as a function of θ for $[+0/90/0]_s$ composite plate under uniaxial compression